

PROFESSIONAL DIRECTION ACTIVITY OF A PRACTICE PSYCHOLOGIST ANALYSIS

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Abstract: In this article, an attempt was made to reveal the psychological aspects of the interests of gifted students.

Key words: Gifted students, family, ability, communication and organization.

A practicing psychologist, for example, a school psychologist, organizes various activities and trainings in order to attract the pedagogical team of the school, students and parents to acquire psychological knowledge, to increase their psychological and spiritual culture, organizes lectures, this is his work of psychological propaganda and propaganda. In order to properly organize these works, a practicing school psychologist must know the duties of psychologists in the educational process. When a psychologist works in the educational system, propaganda In addition, the practitioner publishes articles in psychological scientific and popular magazines and newspapers, and on radio and television is engaged in popularization of psychological knowledge. The methodological tasks of a practicing psychologist in psychological enlightenment and propaganda are as follows.

To provide students with the most basic psychological knowledge and to develop their interest in learning related to acquiring this knowledge, entering into interpersonal relationships with peers and adults, and being able to evaluate their own personal qualities and character traits, abilities, and talents.

Promotion of psychological knowledge through individual conversations, open classes, seminars and consultations, as well as mass media.

A practical psychologist comes to the school primarily for the children. But this does not mean that the psychologist does not work with the teachers. The first obstacle that the psychologist has to overcome in the school is to be able to join the pedagogical team of the school. It is unlikely to succeed in its work if it cannot join a complex organism. Contact with parents is very important in taking the first steps. The initial contact should be voluntary and should be done with the parents themselves. Today, most general secondary schools have their own psychologists. But despite this, the director and teachers often do not have a good idea of what a psychologist can do.

It seems that they will solve it immediately. But when they see that nothing has changed in the psychologist's appearance, they have questions such as, "What is the need of a school psychologist?" the theoretical knowledge learned by a psychologist is not enough. When they come to school, psychologists are often confused by the problems of practice. Although he spends his working time and free time at school, sometimes you can hear the sarcastic words of teachers, "What is our psychologist doing?", "Is the psychologist at school?" If a psychologist does not start his career with self-promotion, he may hear more such sarcasm from teachers. A psychologist must clearly determine the days and hours when he attends classes, talks with teachers, conducts psychological research, gives advice, and conducts psycho-training, and publishes his schedule to the public. It is advisable to have an advertisement about the working hours of the psychologist in at least three places - on the door of the psychologist's room, in the teacher's room, and at the entrance to the school.

The psychologist gives recommendations on developing the achievements and correcting the shortcomings of students' character, monitoring, analyzing, evaluating their behavior, managing their mood and behavior, developing skills and competencies. Practicing psychologists working in general secondary schools have an inestimable role of psychological service in order to prevent social maladjustment of the educational institution from causing their stress.

The activities of the psychological service are focused not only on the diagnosis of the development of mental activity and personal characteristics of students, on the identification of the psychological causes of disorders in education and upbringing, but also on the elimination and prevention of such disorders.

The information identified and collected by such a psychologist implies the need to actively participate in the correction of students. In short, it is not easy to give a lecture and training on Applied Psychology at school. It is necessary to take many factors into account it is necessary to adapt to the audience, to try to satisfy their needs, to present one's image as a beautiful, open-minded person with rich life experience. You should try to read the lectures in a psychologically positive way, try to express your personal thoughts, you can talk about yourself appropriately.

Any audience will be interested in your exemplary life, emotions, and achievements as a psychologist and human being. If the audience is convinced of you as a mature specialist, they will eagerly accept the information and knowledge you give in the lecture. Try to start your lecture in an active and emotional way, activate their attention and invite them to a joint spiritual conversation.

List of used literature:

1. Kayumova, G., & Suyunova, D. (2023). THE ROLE OF PARENTS AND TEACHERS IN THE DISCLOSURE OF A CHILD'S ABILITY. Models and methods in modern science, 2(1), 133-135.

2. Narzullayevna, K. G. (2022). Psychological effects of motivation of marriage in young people on family strength. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 12(6), 301-303.

3. Narzullayevna, K. G. Z., & Kyzi, Y. M. H. (2022). NEGATIVISM IS DESTRUCTIVE AS PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS. Science and innovation, 1(B3), 851-853.